

Education Quarterly Reviews

Çay, Tolga, and AKAY, Cenk. (2021). CELTA Course from the Perspective of EFL Instructors: A Case Study. In: *Education Quarterly Reviews*, Vol.4, No.4, 280-296.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.04.04.392

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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CELTA Course from the Perspective of EFL Instructors: A Case Study

Tolga Çay¹, Cenk AKAY²

¹ Çağ University, Turkey. Email: tolgacay@cag.edu.tr / ORCID ID 0000-0002-6067-2242

² Mersin University, Turkey. Email: cenkakay35@hotmail.com / ORCID ID 0000-0001-9892-6255

Correspondence: Tolga Çay. Email: tolgacay@cag.edu.tr

Abstract

The aim of this study is to explore the CELTA course from the perspective of EFL instructors. A single case study of qualitative research methods is employed in the study. The sample consists of 6 EFL instructors working for a private university in Turkey. The quantitative data of the research was obtained through course evaluation survey. Qualitative data was gathered by open-ended questions and interview forms developed by the researcher and also with the documents. Descriptive analysis was performed to show evaluation of the course in the quantitative phase of the research. On the other hand, the content analysis method was applied in the analysis of qualitative data. As a result of the study, the CELTA course is useful for EFL instructors' careers; nevertheless the course components and content should be redesigned considering andragogic principles. Moreover, EFL instructors were pleased to take the course at the end of the course although the course's weaknesses.

Keywords: CELTA, In-Service Training, EFL Instructor, Professional Development

1. INTRODUCTION

Are teachers trained or are they born as teachers? It is a generally thought the fact that teachers can be trained (Delaney, 2015; Candal, 2015; Knapp, 2012; Daizeabdao, 2016 Osae, 2017; Cruz, 2018). Traditionally, the teachers join a structured training process which provides them to acquire the skills and the competence to accomplish the model of a teacher in various instructional settings. Those processes are commonly based on teacher training or teacher education. In this respect, the teachers who graduated from those faculties continue their life as teachers in public or private schools. Generally in the world, the teachers need a teacher diploma or pedagogical formation to be placed in public schools and universities. However, in some state and private schools or universities, there can sometimes be seen that there are foreign language teachers and lecturers who don't own a teacher diploma or a certificate related to instruction. The only reason why they are hired is they are native speakers or foreigners, likewise Ozturk and Atay (2010) stated that native speakers and foreigners who have less experience of teaching and fewer qualifications than non-native speakers are more often employed particularly by private schools to attract students' and parents' attention. Although they are capable of the language which they teach, they are lack of instructional strategies and methods. The council of higher

education(CoHE) in Turkey has recently issued a decision regarding the employment of international academic staff. In this context, the requirements for the employment of international academic staff were updated with a perspective that primarily focuses on the quality of education.

From this point of view, the minimum requirements for the employment of international academic staff to be employed in the foreign language preparatory classes of higher education institutions were determined. As CoHE (2020) stated that it wouldn't be enough for native speakers to be employed as an English instructors in English preparatory classes. They are required to have at least a Bachelor's degree (BA) in one of the fields such as English Language and Literature, Linguistics, Teaching or Educational Sciences. English native speakers who are not graduates of these majors are required to have at least two years of language teaching experience. Furthermore, it won't be enough for non-native English speakers to have at least a BA in one of the majors, such as English Language, English Literature, and English Language Teaching. They are expected to have at least two years of language teaching experience in an accredited language school that is recognized internationally and to have a DELTA or CELTA foreign language certificate. After this regulation, international academic staff who are currently working in higher education institutions will be given additional time starting from the end date of their contracts to meet the new employment requirements if they are considered as being beneficial because of their work. Contract terms of those who cannot meet the new requirements will not be extended. Thus, many instructors currently working at universities have applied for CELTA. Although there is an obligation for instructors, it shouldn't be assumed as the only reason they apply for CELTA. Beside this obligation, instructors are also willing to participate in CELTA because for their vocational development particularly in teaching English.

When we examined that why CELTA and DELTA are chosen for this requirement, it is seen that the CELTA course has validity internationally for those who would like to instruct English to speakers of other languages. Furthermore, "the trainees," which is called for CELTA participants, take a minimum of 120 sessions of training set up to gain practical skills of teaching. Although CELTA includes 120 sessions of training, CELTA course takes longer period of time. The reason might be in the design of the course. As Thornburry and Watkins (2007, p. 5-6) state, "CELTA as pragmatic, incorporated, experiential, alinement and cogitator program in which trainees employ in activities which provide them connect the theory and practice through observations, assignments and teaching practice." It was formerly known as CTEFLA and it is also one of the most recognized certificate worldwide by not only private schools but also public schools. The CELTA is actually an initial teacher training course which aims to introduce trainees with ELT teaching experience and "prepare those trainees for their entry into the profession" (UCLES/RSA, 1998c.). The aims of the course can be listed as follows: Acquiring essential subject knowledge and familiarity with the principles of effective teaching, acquiring a range of practical skills for teaching English to adult learners, demonstrating their ability to apply their learning in a real teaching context.

The CELTA syllabus covers 5 targeted topic areas such as learners and teachers, and the teaching and learning context, language analysis and awareness, language skills: reading, listening, speaking and writing, planning and resources for different teaching contexts, developing teaching skills and professionalism. The course programmes are provided by a minimum of 120 contact hours with tutors including input, supervised lesson planning, teaching practice, feedback on teaching, peer observation, observation of experienced teachers and consultation time. In this respect, candidates will need to dedicate a minimum of 80 hours for the required reading, research, pre-post session tasks, assignments and lesson preparation.

Candidates are assessed by the tutors within the CELTA during and at the end of the course. There are two components which are planning and teaching, and written assignments related to classroom. It is compulsory for the candidates to present four written assignments. While the first assignment focuses on adult learners and learning contexts, the second assignment focuses on the language system. Furthermore, the third assignment focuses on the language skills, the last assignment needs reflection on classroom teaching and defining of action points.

Besides these four assignments, all the candidates need to lecture for a total of six hours, working with classes at two levels of ability (e.g. A2 and B1). Assessment uses as a base the candidate's overall ability in the sessions with regard to the six hours of teaching practice.

The CELTA Certificate will be presented to candidates who meet the requirements and whose performance meets the criteria in assessment components. At the end of the course the tutors and assessors determine final grades, and candidates' performance need to meet all the descriptors at a specific passing grade such as "Pass," "Pass B" and "Pass A." If any candidate's performance does not meet the descriptors, he/she will be graded by "Fail"

By the end of the course as qualification, candidates who complete the course successfully can start working in a variety of English for Speakers of Other Languages (ESOL) teaching contexts around the world.

Outcome of the course can be defined as, successful candidates at Pass level should show convincingly that they can prepare and plan for the effective teaching of adult learners and demonstrate professional competence as teachers.

Though CELTA is not brand new through Turkish context, it has been lately recognized as an official certificate by the Ministry of National Education and the Council of Higher Education. From this point of view, it may be predictable that more teachers and instructors will take CELTA certificates in the following years. Thus, when the literature is examined both nationally and internationally, it is seen that the researches on CELTA have been arising in the last years, yet the numbers of the studies are limited (Borg, 2002; Constandini, 2011; Sag, 2013; Delaney, 2015; Aydin, 2016; Gulcan & Kesli Dollar, 2016; Florkowska, 2018; Mackenzie, 2018; McArdle, 2019; Birgun, 2020; Sweeting, 2020). However, a few studies (Borg, 2002; Sag, 2013; McArdle, 2019) offered to reveal individual experiences of trainees about the course. Referring to this point, current study is an attempt to give a perspective from the EFL instructors towards CELTA. Since EFL instructors at Cag University School of Foreign Languages are encouraged to have their CELTA qualifications, this study has been carried out on a voluntary basis and a total of 6 language instructors who have taken their CELTA qualifications. Therefore, this is a case study aiming to reveal the trainees' individual experiences and reflections in the context of CELTA. The purpose of the study is to describe the perspectives of 6 EFL instructors on CELTA course. Following questions are investigated to reveal the perspectives of the instructors;

- 1- What were the expectations of EFL instructors on the CELTA?
- 2- What were the needs of the trainees as EFL instructors?
- 3- How did the CELTA affect instructors' classroom practices?
- 4- How did EFL instructors evaluate the CELTA course?
- 5- What suggestions instructors made to improve the CELTA?

2. METHODOLOGY

In this research, to explore the experiences of EFL instructors on the CELTA course a single case study was employed. Case study research is a qualitative approach in which the investigator explores a real-life, contemporary bounded system (a case) over time, through detailed, in-depth data collection (Creswell, 2013). Yin (2009) states that the case study's fundamental is its ability to deal with a variety of evidence sources such as interviews, observations, and documents. Furthermore, what could be available in other sorts of qualitative methods. From this point of view, document analysis, interviews, survey, and open-ended question form were employed. He also explains that use of the case study strategy has a vivid advantage when a "how" or "why" question is examined about a contemporary situation over which the researcher has little or no control. The case study method provides investigators to keep of the holistic and significant idiosyncratic of real-life events (Yin, 2009). Yin (2009) states that "case study research involves study in a real life context or setting" (p. 9).

As for the study's design, a case study was adopted as appropriate since the study does not focus to look for a cause-effect relationship, measuring the objective reality or developing, verifying and confirming any universal theories, but rather it aims to delve into how people interpret the meaning or construct a meaning for a particular situation. In this study, EFL instructors' CELTA experiences have been discussed as a case.

Among several research approaches in qualitative research design, a single case study was considered appropriate to the research problem and the purpose of the current study since it enables a more in-depth analysis of the case.

The data of the study, of which focus is to provide an in-depth understanding of the EFL instructors' CELTA experiences, were gathered through different sources of information. In this study, the purposeful sampling method was adopted which is considered as one of the prevalent methods in qualitative research (Creswell, 2013).

2.1. Study Group

In this research, the study group consists of 6 foreign EFL instructors who work for Cag University Preparatory School. The study group of the research was determined using purposeful sampling method. The age range of these 6 foreign EFL instructors is between 26-60. They speak different languages as their native language and have been using English as a medium of instruction in their classes. The number of female instructors (n=4) outnumbers the number of male instructors (n=2). As for their educational background, the majority of the EFL instructors have experience in teaching for more than 4 years. As for professional development, half of the EFL instructors (n=3) are enrolled in Master's programs while other half (n=3) are have in Bachelor's degree programs. Moreover, half of the EFL instructors (n=3) teach reading & writing whereas the other half (n=3) teach listening & speaking classes. The demographic characteristics of the study group are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographics of Participants

Variables	Category	f	%
Gender	Male	2	33,33
	Female	4	66,66
Age	26-30	4	66,66
	31-45	1	16,66
	46-60	1	16,66
Teaching Experience (Time)	1-3	1	16,66
	4-6	3	50
	7-9	1	16,66
	+10	1	16,66
Degree	BA	3	50
	MA/Ongoing	3	50
Teaching Experience (Location)	Turkey	5	83,33
	Russia	2	33,33
	Holland	1	16,66
	Ukraine	1	16,66
Other Teaching Experiences	Linguistics	1	16,66
	Statistics	1	16,66
Other Languages	Turkish	5	83,33
	Russian	2	33,33
	Dutch	1	16,66
	German	1	16,66
	French	1	16,66
	Norwegian	1	16,66
	Ukrainian	1	16,66
	Korean	1	16,66
	Slovak	1	16,66
	Czech	1	16,66
Lessons They Teach	Reading & Writing	3	50
	Listening & Speaking	3	50
Main Reason for Doing	CoHE Requirement	3	50

CELTA	Self-Improvement	3	50
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In the abbreviations place in the findings section, M for Male and F for Female were utilized. For instance; (M, 2) M symbolizes male, and 2 is participant number.

2.2. Data Collection Tools and Procedure

Data were gathered and analyzed utilizing the recommended implications and sources by Yin (2009).

The current case study database was included and includes the following sources of data:

- 1) Administrative and research based documents: The researchers reviewed the administrative and research based documents about the CELTA course. Those documents include curriculum, course requirements and components of assessment, grading process, assignments, hand book and related researches.
- 2) Interviews: The researcher conducted interviews online via Zoom and they are all recorded. It is aimed to understand of what is being studied deeply. To obtain this depth “the researcher must follow up, asking more question about what was initially heard” (Rubin & Rubin, 2005). Semi-structured questions were introduced and follow up questions also were carried out. Each attempt was occurred to make sure questions were asked in an objective and unbiased manner.
- 3) Survey: A survey, which was prepared by Aine (2019), was performed to the participants to get their views about the evaluation of the course.
- 4) Open-ended Questionnaire: The open-ended question form developed by the researchers was created in order to get the opinions of the instructors about their views on the CELTA course. While preparing the form, the literature was searched and draft questions were created. Then, expert opinions were taken from two faculty members in the field of foreign languages. These two experts also held their CELTA certificates. Final arrangements have been made in line with the feedback they have given and made ready for use in research. The instructors answered the open-ended questions form created through Google Forms online.
- 5) Member checking: A copy of the information gathered from the interviews was provided to the interviewee for the accuracy of interpretation and correction if necessary. The participant reviewed the data and approved.

Figure 1: Data collection tools used in the research

2.3. Data Analysis

The data collection process in the study was carried out by the researcher on the basis of the voluntary participation of the preparatory school instructors. While collecting the data, participants were informed of the

purpose of the study and made sure that the collected data would be kept anonymous and confidential. Data were collected via Google Forms. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the quantitative data.

The content analysis method was employed for the analysis of qualitative data. Content analysis is to bring together similar data within the framework of certain concepts and themes and interpret them in a way that the reader can understand (Yildirim & Simsek, 2005). Content analysis is a scientific approach that allows an objective and systematic examination of verbal, written and other materials (Tavsancil & Aslan, 2001). Qualitative data analysis is a process in which the researcher organizes the data, divides them into analysis units, synthesizes, reveals patterns, discovers important variables and decides what information to reflect on the report (Ozdemir, 2010).

The content analysis was carried out in three stages. In the first stage, the main categories emerging for the goal of the research from the responds given to the research question were determined. In the second stage, the data were arranged by reading according to the main categories previously determined and sub-categories of the main categories were determined. In the last stage, the data are defined according to the main category and sub-categories, and the information that comes up with the necessary quotations is presented in relation to each other. The data gathered with the interviews and open-ended questions form was organized and appropriate themes were created by 2 different experts. Then the coding reliability of the data obtained in the study was calculated using Miles and Huberman's formula ($\text{Reliability} = \text{consensus} / (\text{consensus} + \text{divergence}) * 100$). The fact that the coding among the coders is at least 80% indicates that the research results are reliable (Miles & Huberman, 1994; Patton, 2002).

Table 2: Reliability Coefficient Between Encoders

Question Number	Reliability Coefficient Between Encoders
1.	0.84
2.	0.88
3.	0.80
4.	0.88
5.	0.92
6.	0.85
7.	0.91

2.4. The Trustworthiness of the Research

To ensure the trustworthiness in a qualitative study, several techniques such as transferability, conformability, credibility, and dependability should be validated (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). The combination of those components was utilized to serve the goal of the study. Transferability couldn't be applied because of the conclusions in the current study aren't transferable to other times, contexts, and participants.

For enhancing the credibility, the triangulation method was employed. In the current study, the methodological triangulation was employed by using several data collection tools such as interviews, open-ended questionnaires and surveys.

Moreover, the researchers applied a peer debriefing strategy to develop a brighter understanding of the case. From this point of view, the researcher was helped by another researcher during the coding phase to minimize misinterpretations and eliminate the possible researcher biases.

To establish conformability, audit trails were organized and utilized to eliminate biases by taking a record of process. In this regard, raw data and documents, categories' structures, methodological notes, summaries and proposals were kept.

The last but not the least, to ensure dependability inquiry audit technique was performed. The supervisor of the study as an external researcher monitored and examined the process of the current study, by providing constructive feedback for every single step taken.

3. FINDINGS

In the first research question of the study which is “what were the expectations of EFL instructors on the CELTA,” the codes formed based on the answers they gave to the question “What skills did you expect to gain on the course of CELTA? Did the courses meet your expectations? Please explain briefly.” to learn the views of the instructors about their expectations on the CELTA course.

Table 3: Qualitative Analysis Results of Trainee’s Expectations through the Course

Theme: Expected Skills (N=6)		
Codes	f	%
Teaching adults	2	18
Teaching grammar	2	18
Overall skills	1	9
Classroom management	1	9
Improving own English skills	1	9
Assessing needs	1	9
Lesson planning	1	9
Material designing	1	9
Teaching strategies	1	9
Sum	11	100

According to the table, the code with the highest density was “Teaching adults” (f=2) and “Teaching grammar” (f=2). For example;

“I was expecting like to learn more about teaching adults first, and young adults may be, also I expected more academical knowledge how to explain grammar in a better way not make it so boring as we get used to it. Mostly teaching adults and young adults.”(F,1). “I was expecting to learn how to teach grammar. I didn’t really think about the other skills too much. I thought that would focus on the skills as well as the grammar that what I needed was grammar.” (F,2). “A range of skills for teaching adult learners such as, assessing needs, lesson planning & material design, a variety of teaching strategies for different aspects of language learning.” (F,3).

In the second research question of the study which is “what were the needs of the trainees as EFL instructors,” the themes created based on the answers they gave to the question “Do you think the CELTA course considered your needs in terms of the course content?” to learn the views of the instructors about the course content.

Table 4: Qualitative Analysis Results of Trainee’s Needs

Theme: Meeting Needs (N=6)			
Sub-themes	Codes	f	%
Yes	Focusing on teaching adults	2	25
	Focusing on smaller groups	1	12.5
	Teaching vocabulary	1	12.5
	Teaching grammar	1	12.5
	Teaching reading	1	12.5
No	Pretty basic	1	12.5
	Not even a little	1	12.5
Sum		8	100

According to the table, the code with the highest density was “Focusing on teaching adults” (f = 2). For example; “I think the course is very suitable for me anyway, because I work with adults and this course is mainly focusing on working with adults, teaching adults and also as I noticed, while doing the course usually it focuses on

smaller groups as well although in the last unit they do talk about kids and about bigger groups but in general just smaller groups and mostly adults. It is the kind of groups I teach every day in prep school, that's why I think the course was quite suitable for me.” (F,4). “On the whole it met my needs in. However, the content was pretty basic and in many ways didn't teach me anything that I didn't already know.” (F,3). “Not even a little, the theoretical background in the course is horrendously outdated; we're talking ten years old for the most recent sources they sight and as far as methodological goals or psycholinguistic insides early 2000s, it's very outdated. There is almost no connection between the theoretical background and the practical skills they want you to learn.” (M,1).

In the third research question of the study which is “how did the CELTA affect instructors' classroom practices,” the codes created based on the answers they gave to the question “What changes have occurred in terms of approaches and techniques you use in the class after the CELTA?” to learn the views of the instructors about the course reflection.

Table 5: Qualitative Analysis Results of Trainee's Views on Inclass Changes

Theme: Changes Inclass (N=6)		
Codes	f	%
Giving meaning of vocabulary	3	16
Using breakout rooms	3	16
Drilling techniques	2	11
Being more interactive	2	11
Giving physical approach	2	11
Having group work	1	5
Having pair work	1	5
Being aware of the problems students might encounter	1	5
Knowing how to write lesson plan	1	5
Giving simpler instructions	1	5
Being more polite	1	5
Eliciting information from students	1	5
Sum	18	100

According to the table, the code with the highest density was “Giving meaning of vocabulary” (f=3) and “Using breakout rooms” (f=2). For example;

“I started to use more breakout rooms. I did before but now even I use it more. When you give some task to your students they do it individually. After that you put them into breakout rooms, so they compare their answers, they earn more confidence about their answers. Only then do they come back to the main class, you ask them the answers so you give them the answers. I think breakout rooms, it was a good thing. Also drilling techniques about teaching pronunciation were nice. There are couples of them. They told us to give meaning before forming pronunciation. So first of all we should give the meaning in a context aftexplainingain this meaning when you give them form and you move to pronunciation so there are some drilling techniques for pronunciation, you can give all the sentence drilling it. You can point on a singer and ask for example what is missing. I playing football now. So you can show what is this point “I.”m”. Using your fingers let them understand better like repeating these things.” (F,1). “I definitely know how to write lesson plans better now, I mean before it was so confusing I knew in general how to do it, yeah I didn't know how to start or I wasn't sure about the procedure or structure, now I can do it really faster and doesn't take too much time because I know the structure. Another thing, I learnt a lot of techniques in this course and I'm trying to use them. In general, if I think about the changes that I have applied in my lessons giving simpler instructions, trying to use imperatives more often, trying to elicit everything from the students not just explaining the rule or explanation but trying to elicit everything from the students. According to CELTA, first you need to give the example and then you need to prepare concept checking questions so the students will explain the rule to you.” (F,4).

The codes created based on the answers they gave to the question “What are the contributions of CELTA to your teaching not only academically but also psychologically as a teacher?” to learn the views of the instructors about the contributions of the course.

Table 6: Qualitative Analysis Results of Trainee’s Views on Contributions of the Course

Theme: Contributions (N=6)		
Codes	f	%
Made me more confident	3	37
Made me more tolerant	2	25
Made me more communicative	1	12.5
Made me more calm	1	12.5
Decreased teaching time	1	12.5
Sum	8	100

According to the table, the code with the highest density was “More confident” (f=2). For example; *“It helped to be more calm and my lesson. It teaches you to wait and of course first thing they teach you to decrease your teaching time. To decrease it you should wait for students’ answers like give them more time. We normally expect we ask and the answer should just come after our question. But no we should give them time to think and less emotion take it easy about the lesson. It made me more tolerant.”* (F,1). *“When I teach grammar now, I feel more comfortable, less afraid of teaching something wrong. It was helpful for my classes.”* (F,2). *“I’m more confident about lesson aims so I know what I want from students, I know what the next step should be so I feel more confident during my lessons.”* (F,4).

In the fourth research question of the study which is “how did EFL instructors evaluate the CELTA course,” the themes created based on the answers they gave to the question “From the perspective of a CELTA graduate, what are the strengths and weaknesses of this teacher training course?” to learn the views of the instructors about the evaluation of the course.

Table 7: Qualitative Analysis Results of Trainee’s Views on Strengths and Weaknesses of the Course

Theme: Strengths and Weaknesses of the Course (N=6)			
Sub-themes	Codes	f	%
Strength	Teaching practice weeks	3	12
	Taking feedback from tutors	2	8
	Being online	1	4
	Intense course	1	4
	Teaching reading	1	4
	Helpful tutors	1	4
	Trying to keep trainees working	1	4
Weakness	Outdated materials	3	12
	Not having enough interaction	2	8
	Outdated teaching strategies	1	4
	Limited approaches	1	4
	No units about motivating students	1	4
	Long and boring online units	1	4
	Only small classes	1	4
	No guidance for extra sources	1	4
	Different quality of tutors	1	4
	Working at the same time	1	4
	Being too long	1	4
	Losing motivation	1	4
Sum	25	100	

When Table 7 is examined, it is seen that the views of the instructors about strengths and weaknesses of the course are gathered around 2 (two) sub-themes which are “Strength” (f=11) and “Weakness” (f=14). According to the table, the code with the highest density was “Teaching practice weeks” (f=3) and “Outdated materials” (f=3). For example;

“It is nice that we could do it at the same time as work. We didn’t need to leave the work or spend time outside the city like living other place. It was online so it was comfortable. It was nice. But it has benefits and disadvantages. We lost our motivation at the end. Because it was so long, so much work, you don’t have this energy and enthusiasm to move on. It didn’t really end maybe it was in the middle of the course. Then of course after our 2nd teaching practice we woke up little bit more. In the middle it was very hard to motivate yourself. Before course I was very motivated about it. I wanted to do it doesn’t depend the work.” (F,1). *“As I work full time and have children, it wouldn’t have been possible for me to do full time course, so it’s definitely a benefit for me that it was online because I could do the units whenever I had time and it’s mostly night time. On the other hand, we didn’t have enough interaction with the tutors and other members. I think if we did it face to face, we would have been more involved, probably we would’ve learnt more as well. Although we didn’t have enough interaction, the course was really intense. We always had to do something. I had to do something every day. The best part of the course was 2 teaching practice weeks. I learnt a lot from them. Another weakness, there is one approach and doesn’t matter if you agree or disagree, you have to do it according to their standards if you want to pass the course. You have to follow what you are given.”* (F,4). *“The main strength of the course was teaching practice and feedback from those who observed. The biggest weakness is that some of the teaching strategies are a bit dated.”* (F,3). *“Materials in used, they could be updated, we’ve got library with some books, those books are almost 20 years old. The strong part of CELTA, I would say definitely tutors, they were extremely helpful, in case of any problem we were able to contact them in a short time, they were extremely supportive and kind.”* (M,2). *“Practice teaching it was the most useful part, it was very hard because we had like every day in a week two weeks with practice it was very intensive it was difficult but they were the weeks that we learnt the most. It was very useful and we’ve got very useful feedbacks from the tutors and also they helped us with planning our lessons. The tutors were really good; they were always helping us if we needed some help. If we sent an e mail, they just answered directly like after 1 minute even if it was in the night. It was online and there were lots of online units, some of them were quite long and it was quite boring sometimes, I didn’t really want to do it but I had to so I just try to get through it. It would have been better to have it as a real course I think to interact with others instead of just reading these slides and these exercises on the internet, it was quite boring and some of the materials were a bit old, they could have been updated. We observed a video; in the video someone showed a film to their student it was an old TV and a video cassette. And the classes that we observed, it was filmed classes before, it was usually small classes so it would have been good to see how the teachers were in the big classes as well.”* (F,2).

The codes formed based on the answers they gave to the question “How useful do you think the CELTA course has been for you in your language teaching?” to learn the views of the instructors about the usefulness of the course.

Table 8: Qualitative Analysis Results of Trainee’s Views on Usefulness of the Course

Theme: Usefulness of the Course (N=6)		
Codes	f	%
Quite useful	3	27
Fine for new teachers	2	18
Could be better	1	9
Making easier	1	9
Helpful	1	9
Taught academic vocabulary	1	9
Would rather DELTA	1	9
Not even close	1	9
Sum	11	100

According to the table, the code with the highest density was “Quite useful” (f=3). For example; “I think it has been useful, of course it can be better but as I said before I feel more comfortable now, has become a little bit easier I think I have improved my language teaching but of course I still need to work on it.” (F,2). “It was fairly useful. There were a couple of things that I learnt and now put into practice. But I think the course is fine for new teachers who are starting their careers. I’d rather do a DELTA course for more in depth training.” (F,3). “It was quite useful. From 1-10 it was 10 or 9. It was a nice experience, it wasn’t easy experience at all. We didn’t sleep nights, we’re suffering to survive but it was very useful for our teaching I think. I’m really happy.” (F,1). “Was it useful comparing the amount of time I put in? Not even remotely close. We spent about 240 hours in this course total, a little more maybe if you struggle on the theoretical side and how much energy, how much physical time took next to my job, not at all. Could I just take practical weeks? I would totally recommend it.” (M,1). “Not just techniques but some general information about lesson planning, it was very helpful. And I have actually learnt new academic vocabulary as well. It was quite useful for me.” (F,4). “Most of the strategies, I have been using, maybe I didn’t know what is the proper name of the strategies but I have been dealing with them before, right now I’m definitely able to improve the strategies. I will get much better results with my students in the future.” (M,2)

Results about the EFL instructors’ evaluation on the course are given in Table 9.

Table 9: Descriptive results of evaluation of the CELTA trainees

		$\bar{X}$	Sd
1 Do you think it gave you adequate training in English?		2.83	1.60
2 Do you think it gave you adequate training in teaching skills?		2.16	.75
3 Do you think it gave you adequate training in the needs of different cultures?			3.16 1.47
4 Do you think it was up-to-date at the time you did it?		3.50	1.64
5 Do you think it encouraged you to reflect on your past experiences as a language learner?		2.00	.89
6 Do you think the course encouraged you to be a reflective teacher?	1.33	.51	
7 Do you think it promoted flexibility in using different teaching practices for different situations?		2.50	1.64
8 Do you think that it balanced teacher centred and student centred learning on the course?		2.66	1.63
9 Did it teach you how to teach English?		1.66	.81
10 Did it teach you how to evaluate yourself as a teacher?	1.50	.54	
11 Do you think it promoted flexibility in using different teaching practices for different situations?		2.33	1.36
12 Did it teach you how to use foreign language materials?	2.16	1.60	
13 Did the course teach you how to adapt foreign language teaching materials?		2.00	1.26
14 Did it increase your powers of self-evaluation?		1.50	.54
15 Do you think it taught you foreign language testing and evaluation skills?			2.66 1.21
16 Did you think it was relevant to your needs?		2.16	1.47
17 Do you think it has a good balance between the teaching of English teaching skills and classroom management skills?		2.50	1.37
18 Do you think it prepared you to teach English in the classroom?	2.33	1.50	
19 Did it meet your needs?		2.16	1.16
Sum		2.27	1.01

The average score of instructors’ views on the CELTA course was determined as 2.27. This finding can be interpreted as instructors’ are not pleased at all. The average score corresponds to the “Disagree” level in the scale.

Furthermore, it was also seen that item6 “Do you think the course encouraged you to be a reflective teacher?” is at the lowest level ($\bar{X}$: 1.33) while item4 “Do you think it was up-to-date at the time you did?” is at the highest level ($\bar{X}$: 3.50). Based on these findings, it can be said that instructors didn’t get enough efficiency from the course.

In the fifth research question of the study which is “what suggestions instructors made to improve the CELTA”, the codes formed based on the answers they gave to the question “Are there any topics that you wish to have been taught at the CELTA course? What suggestions would you make to improve the CELTA course?” to learn the views of the instructors about the evaluation of the course.

Table 10: Qualitative Analysis Results of Trainee’s Suggestions on the Course

Theme: Suggestions on the Course (N=6)		
Codes	f	%
Should be live classes	2	16
Should be more interactive	1	8
Could be units for young learners	1	8
Could be units for special needs students	1	8
Should teach how to motivate students	1	8
Should consider individual differences	1	8
Should teach managing bigger classes	1	8
Should redesign order of assignments	1	8
Should teach using the board	1	8
Should teach monitoring students	1	8
Should be more practice	1	8
Sum	12	100

According to the table, the code with the highest density was “Should be live classes” (f=2). For example; “The videos are nice and useful as for teaching but they are kind of old, if they were more modern, using technologies that we used now because technology used in that time that I’m not sure what are they, so it may be more technology oriented. We did mostly online teaching, so they didn’t give us knowledge about using board. As I know other courses they did give this knowledge to teachers.” (F,1). “More updated materials, maybe I would change the order of the assignments we are supposed to deal with. Dealing with CELTA and dealing with job work, it was almost impossible at the same time to do it and then you are losing your motivation.” (M,2). “I think we didn’t have enough interaction with the tutors and other teachers, we most like read the units and do the task. I guess there should be more interaction, I mean every week you should talk to tutors and we didn’t have enough live classes, every week we should have a live class. And the topics they mostly focus on teaching adults but I guess they could be about young learners and the students with special needs as well. Maybe they could give more information about how to motivate students like games and exercises.” (F,4).

4. DISCUSSION

Education has been a way of transferring the culture for years. Since the education is not stable like the culture, there is reciprocal relation between the education and the culture. They are both dynamic processes and more importantly they are both cumulative. On the other hand education is a process of transferring culture and reflecting state’s ideologies. What makes the states, nations and culture? They are actually based on the language. So the language is also like education and culture, which means it’s not stable, it’s dynamic and cumulative. When they are going further also the teaching methods also should be improvable. Therefore, if pre-service training programs are a building block, in-service training programs make those building blocks as mansions. That’s why pre-service programs are not enough when the years gone, so in-service programs are vital in professional life. From this point of view, the researchers of this study have attempted to investigate the in-service program CELTA from the EFL instructors’ perspective.

As a result of the current research, it was concluded that instructors' pleasant about the CELTA course are at a medium level. They found the course useful for their career although the deficiencies of the course. The deficiencies of the course are probably based on the differences of participants' and course context. When the interview findings are examined, it is seen that the course isn't in line with the andragogic components. Thus, the participants found the course very improvable. One and maybe the biggest issue about the course is that the course doesn't consider the needs of the participants which is completely contrary to the andragogic principles (Knowles, 1984). So the methodologies of the course could be useful but not the needs of the participants. While CELTA course gives training based on small and willingly classes, the participants may encounter big and reluctant classes. So participants' actual classes are not an issue at the CELTA course. Gulcan and Kesli Dollar (2016) also stated that the applicability of the course's methodology is fairly limited, because of the differences of actual classes of participants. Yet, trainees' expectations on the course are gathered around teaching adults and as it is seen on the interviews, the course has met the trainees' expectations in that line.

Besides, the participants stated that they are trying to use the techniques, which they learnt on the course, especially related to distance education. And those contributions are reflected in classes such as breakout rooms, drilling techniques, physical approaches, vocabulary teaching techniques. Also the trainees stated that they are more confident, tolerant and calm after the course. So it can be said that the course affect not only the teaching skills but also the psychological aspects of teachers.

Another issue about the course that though it is an expensive course not only as price but also for physical time, the materials that they used on the course are really outdated and that was stated by all the participants and it was seen that a bit awkward during the course. Since the course was conducted online, the participants have stated that they hadn't had enough interaction with the tutors and other participants, and they have also complained about having limited approaches. But they are also pleased with the helpful tutors, constructive feedbacks and particularly with the practice weeks.

The trainees' suggestions in order to improve the weaknesses of the course are they desired live practice classes and more interaction, also units for young learners, managing bigger classes and another significant issue for teachers is using the board; they didn't get any information about using the board because the course was online so the course should redesign their content and techniques by combining face-to-face and online teaching.

The other issue about the course is, the course content is about teaching adults which is appropriate for this research's participants, yet it should be reconsidered for the trainees who are teaching young learners and special needs students, that is an another issue about considering trainees' needs. On the other hand, the context's transition was also mentioned by O'Connor (2011) and Gulcan and Kesli Dollar (2016). When the course program is examined it can be seen that it is standardized for a general scale of trainees without taking into consideration of trainees' individual differences as participants stated it is fine for new teachers. So andragogic principles also recommend taking the trainees' individual differences (Knowles, 1984). Since the course was online because of the pandemic, the participants didn't get enough interaction with the tutors and other trainees, therefore it was an obstacle to share their ideas and do brainstorming which should be presented to the trainees according to andragogic approach (Knowles, 1996; Kurt, 2002). On the other hand, the tutors always gave useful feedback to the participants that is significant in andragogic principles (Knowles, 1984). Moreover, the trainees are introduced with the aims of the course at the beginning of the course, and at the end of the course they are asked that the course met their expectations. The participants of this course are teaching to adult learners so the course content is dealing with also adult learners, it can be concluded that the course content is designed through problem-based and task-oriented learning considering andragogic principles (Knowles, 1984). In that line, there were several teaching practice weeks during the course, and those parts of the course were found the most useful parts by the participants on the course. Hence, it can be said that the course was a bridge between the theory and practice. And as adult learners, the participants are pleased with walking on that pathway as it was useful for their real-life problems.

5. CONCLUSION and IMPLICATIONS

In conclusion, the CELTA course is useful for EFL instructors' careers; nevertheless the course components and content should be redesigned considering andragogic principles. According to the results of the study, the following implications could be stated for implementation:

- 1- Each course programme should be designed considering the trainees' needs.
- 2- The course content should be divided into groups which are for young learners, young adult learners, adult learners and special needs students.
- 3- The course's methodologies numbers may be increasable.
- 4- The course's materials should be immediately updated.
- 5- The teaching practice week's numbers should be increased.
- 6- The course content should be redesigned considering the distance education's conditions.
- 7- The course programme should be in line with the trainees' actual classes.

Beside the implications above, the recommendations for further research are stated below:

- 1- The implementation of the course can be compared with different countries.
- 2- The current study is conducted with the instructors who are working for university; another research can be conducted with different sample that has different context.
- 3- The differentiation among the trainees' background could be investigated with a quasi-experimental study considering the variables such as degree, mother tongue, experience and etc.
- 4- Trainees' beliefs towards EFL teaching and reflections could be investigated with a quasi-experimental study.

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Appendix

Choose the appropriate one. 1-Strongly Agree, 2-Agree, 3-Neutral, 4-Disagree, 5-Strongly Disagree

	STRONGLY AGREE	AGREE	NEUTRAL	DISAGREE	STRONGLY DISAGREE
1. Do you think it gave you adequate training in English?					
2. Do you think it gave you adequate training in teaching skills?					
3. Do you think it gave you adequate training in the needs of different cultures?					
4. Do you think it was up-to-date at the time you did it?					
5. Do you think it encouraged you to reflect on your past experiences as a language learner?					
6. Do you think the course encouraged you to be a reflective teacher?					
7. Do you think it promoted flexibility in using different teaching practices for different situations?					
8. Do you think that it balanced teacher centred and student centred learning on the course?					
9. Did it teach you how to teach English?					
10. Did it teach you how to evaluate yourself as a teacher?					
11. Did it teach you classroom management skills?					
12. Did it teach you how to use foreign language materials?					
13. Did the course teach you how to adapt foreign language teaching materials?					
14. Did it increase your powers of self-evaluation?					
15. Do you think it taught you foreign language testing and evaluation skills?					
16. Did you think it was relevant to your needs?					
17. Do you think it has a good balance between the teaching of English teaching skills and classroom management skills?					

18. Do you think it prepared you to teach English in the classroom?					
19. Did it meet your needs?					